

PREVALENCE OF *MALASSEZIA SPP.* IN SMALL ANIMAL PRACTICE*

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SUMMARY: *The aim of this study was to evaluate the prevalence of Malassezia spp. in dogs and cats, and to assess the relationship between the Malassezia infection and skin diseases and/or external ear canal diseases. A total of 100 animals were examined (67 dogs and 33 cats). The cytological examination of the external ear canal and skin specimens was performed in order to diagnose Malassezia spp. The prevalence of Malassezia spp. in the external ear canal of all examined animals was 49% (49/100), with the significant difference between the occurrence of Malassezia spp. in healthy and diseased animals ($p < 0.05$). The prevalence for animals with skin diseases was 54.5% (18/33), while the prevalence for animals with diseases of external ear canal was 90.9% (10/11). Statistically significant relationship was shown between the findings of Malassezia spp. on cytological examination and the appearance of erythema in dogs ($p < 0.05$) and of excoriation in cats ($p < 0.05$).*

Key words: *Malassezia*, skin diseases, diagnosis, cytology, dog, cat.

INTRODUCTION

Malassezia yeasts are commensal organisms on the skin of humans and animals, but if cutaneous microclimate changes, their number will rise and they will become pathogens (Eidi et al., 2011). The knowledge of them being present in most cases of generalized dermatitis led to the use of antimycotic drugs in therapy, and to the higher number of cured animals (Gaitanis et al., 2013). In some cases, the presence of these yeasts may suggest that animal have some systematic disease (Nutall, 2003; Prado et al., 2008). In addition to the clinical importance of this yeast in small animal practice, the interest for *Malassezia spp.* is increased due to their zoonotic potential.

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According to our knowledge, the study of the presence of *Malassezia spp.* in our country have only been studied in dogs with atopic dermatitis (Milčić-Matić et al., 2010). The aim of this study was to determine the prevalence of *Malassezia spp.* on skin and in the external ear canal in group of animals (healthy and animals with the signs of dermatitis/otitis externa) using simple methods of diagnosis that are available in clinical practice on every day basis.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

In this study, a total of 100 animals were examined (67 dogs and 33 cats). There were 60 clinically healthy animals and 40 animals (32 dogs and 8 cats) with the signs of dermatitis/otitis. For all examined animals, clinical dermatological exam records were made. Dermatological diagnostic methods, such as skin scraping, acetate tape impression smears, cytological examination of skin specimens and native/cytological microscopic examination of specimens collected from external ear canal, were performed. From all examined animals, specimens from the external ear canal were taken, and from animals that showed signs of dermatitis, skin specimens were collected as well. In order to diagnose *Malassezia spp.* cytological examinations of the skin and external ear canal were performed. A sterile cotton swabs were used to collect the material from chosen skin area and the external ear canal. For the preparation of slides for cytology examination, after specimens were air dried, the method of heat fixation was used. May - Grünwald Giemsa method was used for staining the slides, with phosphate buffer pH 7.2. Then, slides were examined by using a microscope immersion oil lens (1000x). Slides were examined for the presence of the *Malassezia spp.* as well as for the presence of inflammatory cells. The result of ≥ 4 *Malassezia spp.* per high power field was used as a benchmark for clinically significant result. In the diagnostic process, results of microscopic examination of slides were considered together with information collected from anamnestic data and clinical exams.

The results were analyzed by statistical software SPSS 17. Student's t-test was performed for numerical data, and Chi-square test was performed to assess the strength of the relationship between certain parameters. Differences of $p < 0.05$ were considered significant.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

There is no established diagnostic standard for the diagnosis of *Malassezia spp.* (Bensignor et al., 2002). Previous research (Cafarchia et al., 2005) has shown that cytological diagnostic method is highly specific, fast to perform, non invasive, cheap and easily available. Due to all of these, cytological diagnosis of *Malassezia spp.* has an important role in everyday clinical practice.

Picture 1. Cytological exam of external ear canal (upper and left arrow: *Malassezia spp.*; right arrow: comeocyte), orig.

Picture 2. Cytological exam of skin samples (left arrow: *Malassezia spp.*; right arrow: achantolytic cell), orig.

Due to all of these, cytological diagnosis of *Malassezia spp.* has an important role in everyday clinical practice. The false positive results connected with cytological examination are insignificant. On the other hand, false negative results can be obtained if there are errors in the way of collecting samples and making slides for microscopic exam (Cafarchia et al., 2005).

The prevalence of *Malassezia spp.* in external ear canal of all-examined animals was 49% (49/100). The literature data show that the prevalence of *Malassezia spp.* is in the range from 10% (Bond et al., 1997) to 49% (Crespo et al., 2000) in healthy animals, and from 19% (Greene, 1998) to 83% (Crespo et al., 2000) in animals with otitis externa. In our study, the prevalence of *Malassezia spp.* in external ear canal (picture 1) of diseased animals was 57.5% (23/40), and 43.3% (26/60) for healthy ones. There was a statistically significant difference between the occurrence of *Malassezia spp.* in the external ear canal of healthy and diseased animals ($p < 0.05$). This result is in agreement with results of previous studies (Cafarchia et al., 2005; Nutall, 2003). The prevalence of *Malassezia spp.* in external ear canal of healthy dogs was 37.1% (13/35), and 52% (13/25) in ear canal of healthy cats. The earlier data have shown that the prevalence of this yeast in the external ear canal of cats range from 10 – 40% (Crosaz et al., 2013).

Table 1: Etiological factors of dermatitis in dogs

Etiological factors	Number of diseased dogs	Malassezia spp. primary factor	Malassezia spp. secondary factor
Malassezia spp.	5	5	0
Demodex canis	12	0	5
Sarcoptes scabiei	2	0	1
Intertrigo	2	0	1
Pyoderma	2	0	1
Atopic dermatitis	4	0	2
Total	27	5	10

On the skin of animals (dogs and cats) with dermatitis (picture 2) *Malassezia spp.* occurred in 54.5% (18/33) cases. For dogs with dermatitis, the prevalence was 55.5% (15/27) of which in 33.3% cases *Malassezia spp.* occurred as primary, and in 66.6% cases as secondary pathogen. For cats, the prevalence was 50% (3/6), with 25% of cases having *Malassezia spp.* as primary and 75% of cases as a secondary factor.

Table 2: Etiological factors of otitis externa in dogs

Etiological factors	Number of diseased dogs	Malassezia spp. primary factor	Malassezia spp. secondary factor
Malassezia spp.	6	6	0
Otodectes cynotis	1	0	1
Demodex canis	1	0	1
Total	8	6	2

In animals with otitis, the prevalence of *Malassezia spp.* was 90.9% (10/11). In dogs with otitis, *Malassezia spp.* was present in all eight cases (100%). Etiological factors of otitis are shown in table 2. In all cases of otitis, the cerumen was dark brown, accompanied by an unpleasant smell. In cats with otitis, *Malassezia spp.* was present in 66.6% (2/3) cases.

There was no statistically significant difference between the presence of *Malassezia spp.* and the way in which animals were kept (indoor or outdoor), as well as the presence of previous diseases.

Location of skin lesion due to *Malassezia* infection was mainly in the area of ear lobes and the head in diseased dogs, and ear lobes, head, neck and tail in diseased cats (chart 1 and 2). In generalized form, *Malassezia spp.* has only been presented in diseased dogs. In diseased dogs, alopecia was the most dominant primary skin lesions (87.5%), and from secondary skin lesions the most common were erythema (66.6%) and excoriations (58.3%). There was a statistically significant relationship between the occurrence of *Malassezia spp.* and appearance of erythema in dogs ($p < 0.05$). In diseased cats, among primary skin lesions, the most common was alopecia (62.5%), while secondary skin lesions such as excoriations and crusts were present in 87.5% cases, followed by erythema (75%). Statistically significant relationship was shown between the findings of *Malassezia spp.* on cytological

examination and excoriation in cats ($p < 0.05$). Similar results were obtained in previous researches (Nuttall, 2003; Čonková et al., 2011). These studies have shown the occurrence of skin lesions in the area of ear lobes is 44.8%, and in head area this value is 25%.

Chart 1. Localization of skin lesions in diseased dogs

Chart 2. Localization of skin lesion in diseased cats

Cytological exam of skin samples taken from dogs with dermatitis/otitis showed that cellular infiltrate consisted of mastocytes was presented in 37.5% of cases, while neutrophils and eosinophils were presented in 33.3% of dogs, and basophils in 29.2% of dogs. Achantolytic cells were present in 16.6% of dogs. In 62.5% of cases coccoid microorganisms were revealed along with *Malassezia spp.* There was no statistically significant relationship between the presence of *Malassezia spp.* and occurrence of these cells.

Cytological exam of samples taken from the external ear canal of diseased dogs showed the incidence of mastocytes as dominant cellular infiltrate (50% of cases), while basophils, eosinophils, neutrophils and macrophages as dominant cellular infiltrate were presented in 12.5% of cases. In three cases, coccoid microorganisms were found along with *Malassezia spp.* (37.5%). There was no statistically significant relationship between the presence of *Malassezia spp.* and occurrence of these cells.

Cytological exam of skin samples taken from cats with dermatitis/otitis showed that cellular infiltrate of neutrophils and basophils was dominant in 25% of cases, while mastocytes and eosinophils were found in 12.5% cases. Achantolytic cells appeared in 25% cases, while in 37.5% of cases coccoid microorganisms were found along with *Malassezia spp.* There was no statistically significant relationship between the presence of *Malassezia spp.* and occurrence of these cells.

Cytological exam of samples taken from the external ear canal of diseased cats showed that in 66.7% cases cellular infiltrate was consisted mostly of neutrophils. Macrophages, eosinophils and basophils were present in 33.3% cases. In all cases, the coccoid microorganisms were presented. There was no statistically significant relationship between the presence of *Malassezia spp.* and occurrence of these cells.

Previous study have shown that *Staphylococcus spp.* often accompanied *Malassezia spp.* dermatitis/otitis (Petrov and Mihaylov, 2007).

Some limitation of this study should also be addressed. The main limitation is relatively small number of diseased animals, which limit the conclusion on the subject of clinical importance of *Mallassezia spp.* presence in the animals. Besides, the cytological examination was used as the sole method for *Malassezia* diagnosis. It could be presumed that the prevalence of *Malassezia spp.* would be higher with usage of both cytological examination and mycological culture methods. Further studies are needed in order to define possible connection between the occurrence of *Malassezia spp.* and the chemicals used for the maintenance of hygiene in animals.

CONCLUSION

The prevalence of *Malassezia spp.* in external ear canal of all examined animals was 49%, with statistically significant difference between the occurrence of *Malassezia spp.* in external ear canal of healthy and diseased animals. In diseased animals with dermatitis the prevalence of *Malassezia spp.* was high (54.5%), with the higher prevalence in diseased dogs (55.5%) then in diseased cats (50%). The prevalence of *Malassezia spp.* in animals with otitis was 90.9%, with the prevalence of 100% and 66.6%, in dogs and cats respectively. Skin lesions due to *Malassezia* infection are mainly localised in the area of ear lobes and head. The most common primary lesion was alopecia, while erythema, excoriations and crusts were the most common secondary skin lesions, with statistically significant relationship between the occurrence of *Malassezia spp.* and appearance of erythema in dogs and between the occurrence of *Malassezia spp.* and appearance of excoriations in cats.

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PREVALENCIA *MALASSEZIA SPP.* KOD ŽIVOTINJA U MALOJ PRAKSI

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Izvod

Ovo istraživanje je sprovedeno u cilju ispitivanja prevalencije *Malassezia spp.* kod pasa i mačaka, kao i utvrđivanja postojanja veze između prisustva *Malassezia spp.* i pojave dermatitisa/otitisa. Ukupno 100 životinja je uključeno u istraživanje (67 pasa, 33 mačke). Radi dijagnostikovanja *Malassezia spp.* vršen je citološki pregled uzoraka kože i spoljašnjeg ušnog kanala. Prevalenca *Malassezia spp.* u spoljašnjem ušnom kanalu svih pregledanih životinja je iznosila 49% (49/100), sa tim da je postojala statistički značajna razlika između prisustva *Malassezia spp.* u ušnom kanalu bolesnih i zdravih životinja ($p < 0,05$). Kod životinja obolelih od dermatitisa prevalenca *Malassezia spp.* je iznosila 54.5% (18/33), dok je kod životinja obolelih od otitisa iznosila 90.9% (10/11). Postojala je statistički značajna razlika između prisustva *Malassezia spp.* i pojave eritematoznih promena kod pasa ($p < 0,05$), kao i prisustva *Malassezia spp.* i pojave ekscorijacija kod mačaka ($p < 0,05$).

Ključne reči: *Malassezia*, bolest kože, dijagnoza, citologija, pas, mačka.

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